

WHAT CAN BE THE BEST METHOD TO TREAT SPIDER VEINS?

The blood vessels that return deoxygenated blood from other parts of the body to the heart and lungs are called veins. When they become thick, full of twists and turns, or get enlarged are called varicose or spider veins. Usually, nerves in the legs and thighs become varicose and can be treated using any of these **spider vein treatments near me San Diego** options.

If you have only a couple of problem areas and they do not cause you any discomfort or bother you appearance-wise, you may decide to just leave them be. However, if they are problems that mar your look and can be uncomfortable, the wisest thing you can do is to seek out an appropriate form of [spider vein treatment la Jolla](#).

Spider vein Treatment:

Compression Stockings:

The first thing your doctor might recommend for **vein treatment near me** is for you to start wearing compression stockings. Lifestyle changes can be beneficial for those who have a minor issue in this area. The options in compression stockings include support pantyhose, over-the-counter gradient compression pantyhose, and gradient compression pantyhose that are only available through a physician's prescription.

Sclerotherapy:

The most used spider vein treatment is known as sclerotherapy. In this method, the **vein doctor near me La Jolla** uses a special needle to inject a chemical into the skin for this

exact purpose. The chemical causes the walls to begin to swell. From there the walls glue together and end up sealing shut. This ceases the blood flow, and from there, scar tissue will arise and heal.

After a few weeks have gone by, the treated spot should show signs of fading, which is exactly what is supposed to happen. This **vein treatment near me in San Jose** does not necessitate the administration of anesthesia. It does not have to take place in the hospital but can take place right in the doctor's office. Shortly after the **vein treatments in California**, the patient will be able to return to their regular activities, including work and school.

An affected area may only need one injection, but it may require to be managed more than once by the doctor. If you require more than one [vein treatment near me San Diego](#), you will have to schedule them every four to six weeks. Following sclerotherapy, the physician may recommend that you wear gradient compression stockings to facilitate the healing process and to minimize any swelling that might take place. This form of spider vein treatment is used all of the time and is highly successful when it is performed properly.

Side Effects of Sclerotherapy:

As with any procedure done to the human body, there are possible side effects to think about. Be aware, though, that the advantages of having sclerotherapy far outweigh the disadvantages.

- If you have this procedure, you may notice raised, red patches on the treated site, that might even sting. You might even develop bruises where the needle entered your skin. This is temporary and will not take long to go away.

- Around the section of skin that has been treated, groups of fine red blood vessels might appear. You also might notice brown lines or spots. These are symptoms that will start to disappear shortly after the therapy has been completed.
- Although it is rare, sometimes lumps of blood can become trapped in a treated vein and can become inflamed. This won't be a serious issue. The swelling can be relieved by applying heat to it and taking an over-the-counter remedy such as aspirin. At your next doctor's visit, the blood that is trapped will be drained by way of a tiny pinprick.

Get rid of unattractive legs, opting for one of the treatments as they offer the chance to enjoy healthy legs.